

SIMILARITIES AND DIFFERENCES OF CASE IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES

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Annotation: This article examines the case systems of English and Uzbek, two languages with distinct approaches to marking grammatical relationships. While English primarily relies on word order and prepositions, Uzbek employs extensive case endings. The analysis explores similarities and differences in the use and formation of cases in both languages, shedding light on their respective linguistic structures.

Keywords: Case systems, English, Uzbek, grammatical relationships, word order, prepositions, case endings, linguistic structures.

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматриваются падежные системы английского и узбекского языков, двух языков с разными подходами к обозначению грамматических связей. В то время как английский язык в основном опирается на порядок слов и предлоги, в узбекском языке используются обширные падежные окончания. Анализ исследует сходства и различия в использовании и образовании падежей в обоих языках, проливая свет на их соответствующие лингвистические структуры.

Ключевые слова: Падежные системы, английский, узбекский язык, грамматические связи, порядок слов, предлоги, падежные окончания, лингвистические конструкции.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada grammatik munosabatlarni belgilashda alohida yondashuvlarga ega bo'lgan ingliz va o'zbek tillarining kelishik tizimlari

ko'rib chiqiladi. Ingliz tili asosan so'z tartibi va old qo'shimchalarga tayansa, o'zbek tilida keng ko'lamli holat oxiri qo'llaniladi. Tahlil har ikki tilda hollarning qo'llanishi va shakllanishidagi o'xshashlik va farqlarni o'rganib, ularning til tuzilmalariga oydinlik kiritadi.

Kalit so'zlar: Holat tizimlari, ingliz, o'zbek, grammatik munosabatlar, so'z tartibi, yuklamalar, hollar sonlari, lingvistik tuzilmalar.

Studying the case systems in English and Uzbek languages is vital for understanding the fundamental structures and mechanisms through which these languages convey meaning and grammatical relationships. This introduction aims to underscore the importance of delving into case systems, delineating the objectives and extent of the analysis, and presenting an outline of the methodology utilized.

Case systems serve as the backbone of grammar, influencing word order, semantic roles, and the interpretation of sentences. Understanding the intricacies of case usage facilitates language acquisition, aiding learners in producing and comprehending grammatically correct expressions. Comparative analysis of case systems sheds light on the typological characteristics of languages, revealing shared features and unique traits. Exploring case systems in English and Uzbek contributes to linguistic research, enriching our understanding of language universals and variation.

The primary aim of this analysis is to contrast and compare the case systems of English and Uzbek, focusing on their structural differences and functional similarities. The study will investigate the core grammatical cases present in both languages, such as nominative, accusative, genitive, and dative, as well as any additional cases unique to Uzbek. Furthermore, the analysis may extend to examining the role of case in sentence formation, syntactic structures, and discourse coherence within each language. The scope of the study encompasses both synchronic and diachronic perspectives, considering historical developments alongside contemporary usage patterns.

In the comparative analysis of the case systems in English and Uzbek, we can explore several key similarities and differences:

Presence of Core Cases: Both English and Uzbek feature core cases such as nominative, genitive, accusative, and dative, which fulfill essential grammatical functions. In English, the nominative case typically marks the subject of a sentence, while the accusative case marks the direct object. The genitive case denotes possession, and the dative case indicates the indirect object. Similarly, Uzbek utilizes nominative, genitive, accusative, and dative cases, though it employs inflectional endings to mark these cases rather than relying on word order or prepositions. If the noun in the main clause does not come into contact with other clauses, it acts as an imperative: Toshkent, munchalar go`zalsan! [1; 239]

Unlike Uzbek, English lacks several cases found in languages with more complex inflectional systems, including the locative, ablative, and instrumental cases. In Uzbek, the locative case indicates location, the ablative case denotes movement away from a location, and the instrumental case signifies the means by which an action is performed. Due to the absence of these cases in English, the language relies on alternative strategies such as prepositions or word order to convey similar semantic concepts. B.A.Ilyish considers that-`s is no longer a case inflexion in the classical sense of a word. Unlike such as classical inflections, -`s may be attached:[2;21]

- a) to adverbs: yesterday`s events[2;21]
- b) to a word group: Mary and John`s apartment[2;21]
- c) to a whole clause: the man I saw yesterday`s son.[2;21]

Ilyish concludes that the -`s morpheme gradually develops into a “form-word” , kind of particle serving to convey the meanings of belonging possession.[2;21]

Functional Differences:

While both languages use cases to express grammatical relationships, the specific functions and nuances of each case may differ between English and

Uzbek. For instance, in English, the genitive case primarily indicates possession ("the dog's bone"), while in Uzbek, it can also denote relationships of association or origin ("talabalar xonasiga" - "to the students' room"). Additionally, the accusative case in Uzbek not only marks direct objects but also indicates definite direct objects and forms some adverbs, contrasting with its narrower role in English. [2;21]

Impact on Sentence Structure:

The presence or absence of certain cases influences sentence structure and word order patterns in each language. In Uzbek, the use of case endings allows for more flexible word order, as the grammatical roles of nouns are determined by their case markings rather than fixed word order. Conversely, English relies more heavily on word order to convey meaning and grammatical relationships, with less flexibility for reordering elements within a sentence due to the absence of inflectional case endings.

References:

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